

Maximizing Simultaneous Social Media Communication: A Study on Purchase Intention among Millennials and Generation Z in the Online Language Learning Industry

Ali Akbar¹, Dina Dellyana²

^{1,2} Master of Business Administration Program, School of Business and Management, Institut Teknologi Bandung, Jl. Ganesha No 10, Bandung, 40132, West Java, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Born in the middle of lock down Covid-19 in Indonesia, Cetta Online Class started their journey and currently has more than 1700 enrolling students in 5 language classes. However, Cetta needs to re-evaluate to be able to win the market and grow their sales, as they enter the market by using social media marketing communication. Cetta needs to know how to utilize more of their firm-created social media and their ongoing students to be able to generate more word of mouth. Studies have found that firm-created social media communication, user-generated social media communication, and E-WOM have a significant positive impact on purchase intention in several countries. All respondents of this study are millennials and members of Generation Z, as Cetta's students are Millennials and Gen Z. This research was conducted for academic purposes and to make recommendations for Cetta Online Class, a company in the service industry and, to be more precise, a brand that operates an online foreign language course. This research uses quantitative linear regression approaches with a survey method and cross-sectional research design. The measuring tools of the study designed by Alrwashdeh, Emeagwali & Aljuhmani (2019) to measure E-WOM and purchase intention; and Schivinski and Dabrowski (2016) to measure firm-created and user generated social media communication. The sampling technique used in this research is purposive sampling. This study involved 444 respondents (64% Gen Z and 36% Millennial). The results showed that: First, E-WOM is the most influential factor, but it is surpassed by simultaneous social media communication, which is an integrated communication strategy that incorporates all three elements, including firm-created social media, user-generated social media, and E-WOM. Second, Gen Z respondents have more influence than millennials, which includes both firm-created and user-generated influence. Millennials exceeded Gen Z in E-WOM by 0.02%. Third, the recommended strategies to maximize simultaneous communication are: create new design, social media creative team recruitment, content contests and challenges, student stories and testimonials, student ambassador program, invest more in service quality and learning journey, create a referral program, and build a strong community.

KEYWORDS: E-WOM, Firm-created Social Media Communication, Gen Z, Millennials, Purchase Intention, User-generated Social Media Communication.

I. INTRODUCTION

Businesses in education sector are growing rapidly especially since the pandemic Covid-19 started. At the same time, the Education service businesses increasing 5.72% in Q2-2021 becoming Rp 88,15 trillion, and that saying that it contributes of 3.37% of national GDP in 2021. The online learning model is now becoming very common in many institutions and even become necessity for various groups [1]. Indonesia's education sector has a huge attention in recent years, along with the increase of Indonesian consumer spending, reflected by the increasing number of Education Technology users. The market size of Indonesian Education Technology is estimated on \$112 million in 2019 and expected to grow at 24.9% annually [2]. The International trade is one of the main variables in the gross domestic product (GDP) calculation, and to ensure the international trade run smoothly a good communication is needed, and language is the main barrier of international communication. In this world, English is the second language to learn after the first language of the country itself [3].

Born in the middle of Lock down Covid-19 in Indonesia, Cetta Online Class started their journey as fully synchronous English Online Course, Founded by Arief Hidayatullah in May 2020. Cetta currently become a holding company offers Five different languages: English, Japanese, Mandarin, and Korean. Cetta Online Class with 4 different product Languages, develop 4 different Instagram accounts, the purpose is to let the Instagram algorithm to catch specified niche market/audience. Cetta's current audience/followers

3635 *Corresponding Author: Ali Akbar

Volume 06 Issue 06 June 2023

Available at: www.ijcsrr.org

Page No. 3635-3656

are primarily from the Gen Z and Millennial age groups, who are fluent at using social media. As a result, Cetta's social media strategy is designed to appeal to and serve these two target markets. The image below (Figure 1) represents the demographic distribution of Cetta Online Class' Instagram followers.

Figure 1. Demographics of Cetta's Instagram followers

Cetta budget spent on FB Ads were keep increasing but not linear to its sales, even though every Cetta Instagram accounts are growing in the number of followers. Marketing is not only about spending budget on advertisement, because it will only contribute on the awareness as the first phase of marketing funnel. Cetta needs to re-evaluate to be able to win the market and grow their sales, as they enter the market by using social media marketing communication. Cetta needs to know how to utilize more their firm-created social media, and their ongoing students to be able to generate more word of mouth.

Cetta need to be able to scale up by enhance company's business model and marketing strategy, so the company have more budget to spend on company team development rather than too much spend on advertisement. Therefore, further research is needed to understand and analyze about Cetta's purchase intention in a customer centric way. Of course, with the majority of Cetta's current audience and students being Gen Z and Millennials, Cetta must acknowledge that there are differences in approaching and engaging these two markets.

Based on the previous explanation, this study aimed to ascertain which communication method - Firm-Created, User-Generated, or Electronic Word of Mouth - has the most significant influence on Purchase Intention, to learn about certain aspects/variables for approaching both the Millennial and GenZ markets effectively, and to provide actionable recommendations for Cetta Online Class to enhance its marketing strategy.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Social networking via online media, where content is initiated, created, distributed, and consumed by and for its users as a means of exchanging user experiences about goods, services, people, and problems [4]. Content marketing is an approach for distributing relevant and helpful content to a specific target audience in the hopes that they will interact with it and leave comments. Through various Web 2.0 digital channels, such as blogs and social media applications, institutions and organizations can develop their own identities and disseminate information about their products. The idea behind this approach is that customers can share their thoughts and experiences while also learning more about these products. Awareness, association, research-ability, action, and sharing are the metrics used to measure content marketing [5].

Social media platforms like Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube has been established to offer their users a variety of contents. They also used to promote brand-related content and product usage information that was created by their users and was available to users worldwide [6]. As a result, firm-created social media communication is becoming trendy and is seen as an essential component of marketing strategy. Marketers are utilizing social media to interact with platform users and shape their perceptions of their products,

with the goal of converting loyal audiences into loyal customers by understanding audience behavior [7]. The differences between firm-created social media communication with the traditional one is the potential ability of social media to get massive demographic appeal [8].

The world's society produces and publishes social media content, which has evolved into a valuable source of online knowledge known as user generated content. One of the definitions for user-generated content (UGC) is "published content on a publicly accessible website on a social networking site that needs to demonstrate a certain amount of creative effort, and it has been created outside of professional routines and practice." [8]. This content has the potential to influence user relatives by expressing individual viewpoints and opinions about particular goods or brands [9].

A. Word of Mouth (WOM) and Electronic Word of Mouth (E-WOM)

Word of Mouth (WOM) is a marketing communication model in which individuals share information about products with others. In the context of this research topic, which focuses on online courses, the level of student satisfaction plays a crucial role in shaping their WOM communication with their acquaintances, including potential students. WOM is undeniably one of the most valuable and effective promotional methods for attracting more students, as it has the ability to capture the attention of potential students. The key elements of WOM that make it compelling are the attractiveness, usefulness, and expertise of the sources, as well as the strength of social relationships and the trust established between individuals [10].

WOM is a communication process in which individuals or organizations provide recommendations on their own behalf for a product or brand. Undeniably, it holds more prestige and influence compared to other forms of marketing communication [11].

WOM in marketing is an intentional activity that occurs through person-to-person intermediaries, whether through oral, written, or digital means, to share experiences related to purchasing products, services, or brands. Electronic word of mouth (E-WOM) refers to the electronic means of spreading WOM, utilizing various digital technologies or the internet [12]. EWOM is defined as an excessive amount of positive or negative comments made about a product, service, or brand to many people online, such as through forums, chat rooms, social media threads, or video posts [13]. E-WOM is often described as a tool for communication between previous customers who have tried a product but have never met or even know each other. It acts as a means to spread information about a product or brand. In response to the development of technology and the internet, E-WOM has evolved from traditional WOM and can be both advantageous and harmful [14]. Research has been conducted to identify the motives that can be transferred from traditional WOM to E-WOM. The indicators of E-WOM are described as follows [15]:

1. Platform assistance, is the consumer trust within the platform used.
2. Venting negative feelings, is the desire to express dissatisfaction as a consumer after consumed a product or brand.
3. Concern for other consumers, is a sincere aspiration to give recommendations for other consumers.
4. Extraversion/positive self-enhancement, is the desire of consumers to share their consumption experiences to enhance self-image as a smart buyer.
5. Social benefits, is the eagerness to share information and interact with the social environment.
6. Economic incentives, is the desire to obtain incentives from the company.
7. Helping the company, is the devotion of consumers to help the company.
8. Advice seeking, is the need to seek advice and recommendations from other consumers.

Even though UGC is commonly considered similar to the concept of e-WOM, they are actually not the same. Undoubtedly, e-WOM refers to any statement made by potential, current, or former customers about a product or brand, encompassing both positive and negative comments, which are shared with their relatives, the public, or a large number of users [16]. On the other hand, UGC focuses on influencing other individuals [17]. UGC holds stronger relevance and a shorter distance between the source and the information, which fosters trust between users and content publishers [18]. As a result, UGC greatly enhances brand image, brand knowledge, and even influences brand perception [19].

B. Purchase Intention

Purchase intention represents the likelihood that a potential customer will make a future purchase of a good or service. Higher purchase intentions will increase the likelihood of either buying or selling. Purchase intent is a crucial indicator that can be used to study consumer behavior. Positive brand commitment leads to positive purchase intentions, which influence consumers to make the actual purchase of the good or service [20].

1) **Firm-Created Social Media Communication and Purchase Intention:** As mentioned earlier, firm-created social media communication refers to accounts created by companies on social media platforms as part of their marketing channels, where they actively create and upload content. Studies have found that firm-created social media has a significant positive impact on online shopping purchase intention in China [21].

2) **User-Generated Social Media Communication and Purchase Intention:** Refers to every content that is written, video taken, and created by consumers and shared through their personal social media accounts. Studies have also found that user-generated social media communication has a significant positive impact on purchase intention in Korea [22].

3) **Electronic Word-of-Mouth (E-WOM) and Purchase Intention:** The digital version of traditional Word of Mouth, which involves consumers sharing their experiences and opinions about products and services through online channels, particularly social media. Studies have found that E-WOM has a significant positive impact on purchase intention among Korean consumers [23].

C. Gen Z and Millennials

Generation Z and Millennials are terms used to describe individuals born within specific time periods. Millennials are born between 1981 and 1996, while anyone born from 1997 onwards is categorized as the new generation, also known as Gen Z [24]. The interconnectivity between generations is influenced by the experiences they have gone through, which shape their behavior. However, decision-making is a fundamental aspect that plays a major role in differentiating among generations. While society often considers Generation Z and Millennials to be the same, they are actually distinct from each other. Many experts and marketers have given names to generations born after 2000, such as post-Millennial, net generation, or Gen Z, due to their high level of technology dependence. Gen Z is also characterized as native users of social networking sites, easily influenced by them, and actively providing feedback on products and services they engage with [25].

Millennials are enthusiastic about sharing their experiences, purchases, and consumption on social media because they find it gratifying. About 37% of Millennials reported feeling like they are "missing something" when they are away from platforms like Facebook or Twitter for a day. Although Millennials make up an estimated 21-26% of the population, they account for 33-35% of global retail spending, equivalent to around \$250 billion. Additionally, data shows that they heavily use smartphones to access the internet and are technology-savvy, allowing them to stay connected with brands anytime, anywhere. They actively engage with brands through social media by following their accounts and liking posts, including product reviews [25, 26]. The Millennial generation perceives themselves as living in a materialistic society, which psychologically influences their consumption behavior more than previous generations [27]. Generations defined by their born year is seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Generations Defined by Their Born Year [24]

D. Conceptual Framework

Based on the theoretical research explained above, the main objective of this study is to examine the impact of Firm-created social media communication, user-generated social media communication, and electronic word-of-mouth on purchase intention. The relationship between these variables is depicted in the diagram below (Figure 3):

Figure 3. Conceptual Framework

In addition to the framework above, the hypothesis will be:

H1: Firm-Created (FC) social media communication has a significant positive influence on Purchase Intention (PI).

H2: User-Generated (UG) social media communication has a significant positive influence on Purchase Intention (PI).

H3: Electronic Word-of-Mouth (E-WOM) has a significant positive influence on Purchase Intention (PI).

III. RESEARCH METHODS

A. Research Design

This research uses quantitative linear regression approaches with a survey method and cross-sectional research design. The process is illustrated by the diagram below (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Research Design

B. Data Collection Method

As this is a quantitative research study, the data was collected using a survey method to gather individual opinions. The information was obtained through an online questionnaire administered to respondents. The first questionnaire items by Alrwashdeh et al. [28] were used to measure the E-WOM and Purchase Intention. The research model measurement for this study meets the required cut-offs of a good model fit. The second questionnaire items by Schivinski and Dabrowski [29] were used to measure the Firm-Created social media communication and User Generated social media communication. The Cronbach's α values for each scale were above 0.70. The coefficients ranged from 0.92 to 0.97, which shows the internal consistency of each scale.

The sampling technique used in this research is purposive sampling, which is a non-probability sampling method that involves intentionally selecting participants who possess specific characteristics relevant to the research objectives. The respondents are categorized into two data categories:

1. **Primary Data:** This includes data collected directly from individuals who have been exposed to the brand Cetta Online Class, such as current students, former students, graduates, and non-students who are part of the Cetta community and potential future students. The total population of respondents for this category is 444, determined using a random sampling technique.
2. **Secondary Data:** This category includes data obtained from existing literature, articles, magazines, journals, and online sources related to the research topic.

C. Data Analysis Method

Data analysis in this research involves several statistical techniques, including descriptive statistics, regression diagnostics, and comparative analysis between Generation Z and Generation Millennial. The analysis was performed using IBM SPSS Statistics 23 software.

1. **Assumptions test**
 - a. **Normality Test:** This test determines whether the data follows a normal distribution. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is used for this purpose.
 - b. **Linearity Test:** The linearity assumption is tested to ensure that the relationship between variables is either linear or non-linear. This helps validate the regression model's assumption of a straight-line relationship between variables.
 - c. **Heteroscedasticity Test:** The heteroscedasticity test examines whether there is unequal variance among the residuals in the regression model.
2. **Linear Regression Analysis:** Linear regression analysis is used to predict or assess the impact of an independent variable on a dependent variable. It estimates the mean value and the value of the dependent variable based on the values of the independent variable.
3. **Comparative Analysis between Generation Z and Millennial:** This analysis compares the influence of independent variables on the dependent variable, specifically focusing on the differences between Generation Z and Millennial. The purpose of this analysis is to provide strategic solutions for businesses when interacting with and targeting the Gen Z and Millennial markets.

D. Customer Persona

The first persona to be described is the Gen Z persona (Figure 5).

Persona of Cetta's Gen Z student

Persona Story

Sarah, is a 17-year-old Indonesian Gen Z student with aspirations to study in China. She comes from a middle-class family and attends a local high school in Jakarta. Sarah is an ambitious and academically-driven student who recognizes the opportunities available for scholarships and personal growth by pursuing her education in China.

Pains/motivations

- **Study in China:** Sarah's primary goal is to pursue higher education in China due to the availability of scholarships and the growing importance of the Chinese language.
- **Mandarin Language Proficiency:** Sarah is motivated to learn Mandarin fluently to meet the language requirements for studying in China.
- **Convenience and Flexibility:** Sarah appreciates the flexibility of online courses that allow her to study Mandarin at home after school.

Challenges

- **Limited Time:** Sarah is juggling her high school curriculum, extracurricular activities, and preparations for college entrance exams.
- **Self-Motivation:** Sarah needs to stay motivated and disciplined to complete the course independently. She may encounter occasional distractions or difficulty in managing her study schedule effectively.

Figure 5. Gen Z Persona of Cetta Online Class Student

The second persona to be described is the Millennial persona (Figure 6).

Persona of Cetta's Millennial student

Persona Story

Ryan is a 28-year-old millennial professional working in the marketing industry in a major city. Ryan is ambitious and driven to advance his career and increase his earning potential. He believes that improving his English language skills will open doors to better job opportunities and higher salaries.

Pains/motivations

- **Career Advancement:** Ryan's primary goal is to advance his career and achieve higher levels of professional success.
- **Higher Salary:** He believes that improving his English proficiency will make him a more valuable asset to his current employer or attract higher-paying job opportunities in multinational companies.
- **Communication and Networking:** He wants to enhance his English language abilities to confidently engage with international clients, colleagues, and industry professionals.

Challenges

- **Limited Time:** may struggle with finding a balance between work, personal life, and learning commitments.
- **Confidence Building:** Ryan may face some self-doubt or lack confidence in his English speaking abilities, especially when it comes to professional settings.

Figure 6. Millennial Persona of Cetta Online Class Student

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The total data collected was 444 respondent who voluntarily answered all questionnaire from online form, which includes 284 people are Gen Z (64%) and 160 people are Millennial (36%) (Table I).

Table I. Data Frequency

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
Valid	Gen Z	284	64.0	64.0
	Gen Millennial	160	36.0	36.0
	Total	444	100.0	100.0

A. Normality Test

Normality test is conducted to check is the data is normally distributed or not, with the minimum standard for significance is 0.05 or 5%. The result of Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test shows significance of 0.2, which means that the data is higher than 5%, and meet the standards to move forward to the next test (Table II).

Table II. One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test		
		Unstandardized Residual
N	444	
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	3.17267396
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.028
	Positive	.026
	Negative	-.028
Test Statistic		.028
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}
a. Test distribution is Normal. b. Calculated from data. c. Lilliefors Significance Correction. d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.		

Besides Kolmogorov-Smirnov test, the normality test data is also supported by the Plot of Regression Standardized Residual. The graph obtained from SPSS 24 output turns out the points really close to the diagonal line, so it can be concluded that the regression model is normally distributed, as shown below (Figure 7):

Figure 7. Normality Test P-P Plot

B. Linearity Test

Linearity test is conducted to test if the dependent variables have linear relationship or not. The significance maximum standard is 0.05, so if the result is under 0,05 means that it has linear relationship between the dependent and independent variables. The results can be seen in these following tables (Tables III-V).

1) FC x PI:

Table III. ANOVA table of FC x PI

ANOVA Table

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Purchase Intention * Firm-Created SocMedCom	Between Groups	(Combined)	1211.915	10	121.192	9.821	0.000
		Linearity	1152.457	1	1152.457	93.393	0.000
		Deviation from Linearity	59.458	9	6.606	0.535	0.849
	Within Groups		5343.191	433	12.340		
	Total		6555.106	443			

2) UG x PI:

Table IV. ANOVA Table of UG x PI

ANOVA Table

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Purchase Intention * User Generated SocMedCom	Between Groups	(Combined)	1359.603	10	135.960	11.331	0.000
		Linearity	1292.397	1	1292.397	107.710	0.000
		Deviation from Linearity	67.206	9	7.467	0.622	0.778
	Within Groups		5195.503	433	11.999		
	Total		6555.106	443			

3) E-WOM x PI:

Table V. ANOVA Table of E-WOM x PI

ANOVA Table

			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Purchase Intention * E-WOM	Between Groups	(Combined)	2106.349	19	110.860	10.566	.000
		Linearity	1684.012	1	1684.012	160.499	.000
		Deviation from Linearity	422.337	18	23.463	2.236	.003
	Within Groups		4448.757	424	10.492		
	Total		6555.106	443			

All the significance result of the “combined between group” shows score of 0.000 which under 0.05, so it means that all independent variables have linear relationship with the dependent variable. The data is qualified to be used for regression analysis.

C. Heteroscedasticity Test

Figure 8. Heteroscedasticity Test Result

The output scatterplots in Figure 8 are showing that:

1. The spread of the dots are on the top, under, and around the zero point.
2. The dots is not swarming only on top or under zero point.
3. The spread of the dots is not making any pattern, such as wavy, broaden or narrowed.

It can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity problem with the data, so a good and ideal regression model can be made.

D. Linear Regression Analysis

1) *Simultaneous*: The results can be seen below (Table VI).

Table VI. Simultaneous Regression for FC, UG and EWOM towards PI

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.565 ^a	.320	.315	3.183	2.086

a. Predictors: (Constant), E-WOM, Firm-Created SocMedCom, User Generated SocMedCom

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

As shown on the R square table of score 0.32 means that FC, UG and EWOM have 32% contribution towards PI, with significant F test 0.000 (<0.05) which means that FC, UG and EWOM has significant influence simultaneously towards Purchase Intention (Table VI).

2) *Partial*: The results can be seen in Tables VII-IX.

1. FC x PI

Table VII. Partial Regression for FC towards PI

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.419 ^a	.176	.174	3.496	1.965

a. Predictors: (Constant), Firm-Created SocMedCom

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

As shown on the R square table of score 0.176 means that FC have 17.6% contribution towards PI, with significant value 0.000 (<0.05) which means that FC has significant influence towards Purchase Intention (Table VII).

2. UG x PI

Table VIII. Partial Regression for UG towards PI

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.444 ^a	.197	.195	3.451	1.977

a. Predictors: (Constant), User Generated SocMedCom

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

As shown on the R square table of score 0.197 means that UG have 19.7% contribution towards PI, with significant value 0.000 (<0.05) which means that UG has significant influence towards Purchase Intention (Table VIII).

3. EWOM x PI

Table IX. Partial Regression for EWOM towards PI

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.507 ^a	.257	.255	3.320	1.924

a. Predictors: (Constant), E-WOM

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

As shown on the R square table of score 0.257 means that EWOM have 25.7% contribution towards PI, with significant value 0.000 (<0.05) which means that EWOM has significant influence towards Purchase Intention (Table IX).

E. Comparative Analysis of Gen Z and Millennial

Now the linear regression analysis is conducted one more time as comparative study between Gen Z and Millennial respondent.

1) **Linear Regression Simultaneous:** The results can be seen in Tables X and XI.

• Gen Z

Table X. Simultaneous Regression for FC, UG and EWOM towards PI among GenZ Respondent

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.588 ^a	.346	.339	3.124

a. Predictors: (Constant), E-WOM, Firm-Created SocMedCom, User Generated SocMedCom

The R square shown on the table score is 0.346, meaning that FC, UG and EWOM have influence towards the Purchase Intention by 34.6% among Gen Z respondent (Table X). Significant F test 0.000 (<0.05) which means that FC, UG and EWOM has significant influence simultaneously towards Purchase Intention among Gen Z respondent.

• Millennial

Table XI. Simultaneous Regression for FC, UG and EWOM towards PI among Millennial Respondent

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.538 ^a	.290	.276	3.222

a. Predictors: (Constant), Firm-Created SocMedCom

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

The R square shown on the table score is 0.290, meaning that FC, UG and EWOM have influence towards the Purchase Intention by 29% among Millennial respondent (Table XI). Significant F test 0.000 (<0.05) which means that FC, UG and EWOM has significant influence simultaneously towards Purchase Intention among Millennial respondent.

2) **Linear Regression Partial:** The results can be seen in Tables XII-XVII.

1. **FC x PI**

- Gen Z

Table XII. Partial Regression for FC towards PI Among Gen Z Respondent

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.422 ^a	.178	.175	3.489	1.925

a. Predictors: (Constant), Firm-Created SocMedCom

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

- Millennial

Table XIII. Partial Regression for FC towards PI Among Millennial Respondent

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.406 ^a	.165	.160	3.472	2.077

a. Predictors: (Constant), Firm-Created SocMedCom

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

The R square shown on the table for Gen Z score is 0.178 and for millennial is 0.165 meaning that FC have influence towards the Purchase Intention by 17.8% among Gen Z respondent and 16.5% among Millennial respondent (Tables XII and XIII). Significant F test for both GenZ and Millennial is 0.000 (<0.05) which means that FC has significant influence simultaneously towards Purchase Intention among Gen Z and Millennial respondent.

2. **UG x PI**

- Gen Z

Table XIV. Partial Regression for UG towards PI Among Gen Z Respondent

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.462 ^a	.213	.210	3.414	2.015

a. Predictors: (Constant), User Generated SocMedCom

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

- Millennial

Table XV. Partial Regression for UG towards PI Among Millennial Respondent

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.399 ^a	.159	.154	3.485	1.968

a. Predictors: (Constant), User Generated SocMedCom

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

The R square shown on the table for Gen Z score is 0.213 and for millennial is 0.159 meaning that UG have influence towards the Purchase Intention by 21.3% among Gen Z respondent and 15.9% among Millennial respondent (Tables XIV and XV). Significant F test for both Gen Z and Millennial is 0.000 (<0.05) which means that UG has significant influence simultaneously towards Purchase Intention among Gen Z and Millennial respondent.

3. EWOM x PI

- EWOM x PI Gen Z

Table XVI. Partial Regression for EWOM towards PI Among Gen Z Respondent

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.513 ^a	.264	.261	3.303	1.954

a. Predictors: (Constant), E-WOM

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

- EWOM x PI Millennial

Table XVII. Partial Regression for FC towards PI Among Millennial Respondent

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.515 ^a	.266	.261	3.257	1.984

a. Predictors: (Constant), E-WOM

b. Dependent Variable: Purchase Intention

The R square shown on the table for Gen Z score is 0.264 and for Millennial is 0.266 meaning that EWOM have influence towards the Purchase Intention by 26.4% among Gen Z respondent and 26.6% among Millennial respondent (Tables XVI and XVII). Significant F test for both Gen Z and Millennial is 0.000 (<0.05) which means that EWOM has significant influence simultaneously towards Purchase Intention among Gen Z and Millennial respondent.

F. Analysis

Table XVIII. Result from Combined Respondent

Combined Respondent		
	Variable	Influence
Simultaneous	Firm-Created, User Generated, EWOM x Purchase Intention	32%
Partial	Firm-Created x Purchase Intention	17.6%
	User Generated x Purchase Intention	19.7%
	EWOM x Purchase Intention	25.7%

Table XIX. Comparative Result from Gen Z and Millennial Respondent

Comparative Respondent			
	Variable	Influence	
		Gen Z	Millennial
Simultaneous	Firm-Created, User Generated, EWOM x Purchase Intention	34.6%	29%
Partial	Firm-Created x Purchase Intention	17.8%	16.5%
	User Generated x Purchase Intention	21.3%	15.9%
	EWOM x Purchase Intention	26.4%	26.6%

All test results show that all variables have a significant influence on purchase intention, with the simultaneous variable having the greatest influence, while partially EWOM has the greatest influence over Firm-Generated Social Media Communication and User Generated Social Media Communication. Result from combined respondent can be seen in Table XVIII.

After comparing Gen Z and millennial respondents, it was discovered that Gen Z has a higher influence level simultaneously and partially on all aspects except EWOM Table XIX. This implies that Gen Z has a higher level of adaptation to technology than

Millennials, particularly in social media, as the difference between Gen Z and Millennials in the User Generated x Purchase Intention variable is quite large.

G. Business Solution

1) Maximize Simultaneous Media Communication: Simultaneous media communication means Cetta should strive for a balanced and integrated communication strategy that incorporates all three elements, including firm-created social media, user-generated social media, and e-WOM. Means that simultaneous strategy needs to be focused, as the simultaneous influence of firm-created content, user-generated content, and e-WOM is the highest (32% for combined respondent, 34.6% for Gen Z, and 29% for Millennials).

a) Firm-Created Social Media Communication Implementation Plan

After all, Cetta's Instagram and TikTok accounts should continue to prioritize content creation and other digital marketing activities. This includes regularly posting current, informative, and interesting content about trending news, cultural information, and language learning tips, as well as Facebook Ads activities. Cetta must invest in three things in order to strengthen her social media presence, particularly on Instagram.

1. New Design. Based on the findings, it has understood that Gen Z has a greater influence, particularly in the Firm-Created Social Media variable. As a first step in the simultaneous strategy mentioned above, Cetta should create a new design that aligns with Gen Z tastes, offering a fresh and appealing look. Figure 9 shows Cetta's feed before update.

Figure 9. Cetta's Feed before Update

The current design trends used by EdTech companies (Figure 10) targeting the Gen Z market in 2023 emphasize the main phrases/words on their content covers. As some of the references below show, this is typically accomplished by placing a background behind the text to create emphasis.

Figure 10. Examples of Indonesian EdTech Firms that Cater to the Gen Z Market.

Cetta has begun uploading the new feeds into Cetta’s accounts in order to quicken the rebranding schedule. We concentrate on simplifying the colors and emphasizing the words or phrases on the cover of the content so that Gen Z audience are able to view it simpler. As a result, their new feeds appear as follows (Figure 11):

Figure 11. Cetta’s Instagram Feed After Update

2. **Social media creative team recruitment.** As stated in the company profile, Cetta's social media has been led solely by Ali as CEO, with assistance from each head of Cetta's language class departments. Recently, a social media manager has been hired to manage all social media activities. This hiring is required to improve audience targeting, choosing suitable communication for the audience, and comprehensive analysis in carrying out the company's social media activities. Here are three positions that Cetta needs to recruit:

- a. **Senior Content Writer**, one man to standardized the written Carousel Content for every Cetta's Instagram account, lead every content writer and supervise the content before it can be uploaded.
- b. **Specified Social Media Specialist**. Cetta is currently only have one social media manager who leads all video content creators for all 4 language department. one person each language department as social media specialist who understand specified niche market is needed, so all content creators can be led efficiently and effectively.
- c. **External content creators**. As stated in the company profile, Cetta's content creators are the teachers themselves. A dedicated content creator with additional energy and creativity is required to produce more optimal content. Because they do not teach in cetta, their expertise and ideas can be effectively implemented for maximum impact.

Cetta will need to invest some cash from their marketing budget in order to implement these suggestions. As a result, as their Facebook Ads expenses continue to rise on a monthly basis, Cetta must reconsider and reallocate their budget allocations. Cetta also need to consider about investing in talent acquisition and allocating a budget for training and development, especially in areas like brand building and social media management. This will improve their ability to effectively engage with their target audience.

b) User-Generated Social Media Communication Supporting Plan.

The second variable in simultaneous social media communication is user-generated social media communication. According to the literature review, UGC should be authentic content generated by users, therefore, the recommendations plan will focus on persuading users to do so rather than requesting them specific scenario content.

According to the results above, UGC has a much greater influence on purchase intention within the Gen Z market than in the Millennial market. Therefore, it is important to adapt these recommendations to align with Gen Z's communication style.

a. Content Contests and Challenges

- Hold regular contests or challenges, Cetta can encourage students to create content by asking students to upload a video/screenshot of their class study experience.
- Make sure to tag Cetta's Instagram account so that it can be reposted, and voting can be done among Cetta's followers via Instagram story voting.
- As Gen Z loves to strive for rewards, Cetta can give the best entries a prize, such as a discount or other reward.

b. Student Stories and Testimonials

- Encourage students to share their personal stories about how Cetta has aided them in their learning journey; this can be more appealing to Gen Z by using a reels video with an Instagram Collaboration Post.
- Students who are asked to create testimonial videos should be individuals who appear open, talkative, rather than stiff, and ideally have an extensive number of followers on their profiles.
- Provide an incentive like discounts or other rewards to the best entries.

c. Student Ambassador Program

- Establish a student ambassador program. Scout a talented and passionate from Cetta's students and offer them a reward if they want to represent Cetta.
- Reward can be commissions, or free classes, and mentoring about self-development, and digital marketing, which improving their way as an ambassador.
- Ambassador program is not only generating more UGC, but it also helps to build a stronger community around Cetta and contribute in various capacities that are in accordance with Cetta's mission and values.

All of the suggestions listed above are typically implemented by startups today that target the Gen Z market, particularly those with a strong presence on social media and strive to maintain it. For example, Lingotalk (Figure 12), one of the leading Edutech App-based companies in Indonesia, implemented a student ambassador program to enhance their brand awareness. The company recruits student ambassadors through an open recruitment process, offering them various benefits, including sales commissions.

Figure 12. Lingotalk Student Ambassador Recruitment Poster

The second example is a collaboration post of Instagram reels, which Cetta had never done before. Cetta has created lots of testimonial content and uploaded it to Cetta's Instagram account as one of the Firm-Created social media content, with the primary objective to promote the content through Facebook Ads. As seen in the Figure 13, the testimonial contents gained hundreds and thousands of likes thanks to the Facebook Ads system.

Figure 13. Post of Cetta's Testimonial Reels Videos

In comparison, @mudacumasekali (Figure 14), owned by Aldi Pramudya, offers a video learning product that teaches techniques and tips on becoming a content creator, bringing his brand name of @contentacademy.id. They proved successfully that using the collaboration post feature on Instagram Reels can generate a high level of engagement, as confirmed by the numerous comments on the post. This is possible because the uploaded Reels post appears in the feeds of both firm and user accounts, increasing the trustworthiness for those who see it.

Figure 14. Collaboration Post of @mudacumasekali Testimonial Reels Videos

After all, the important point in influence a UGC is to allow the users to maintain their own voice and creativity. This will ensure the content remains authentic and relatable.

c) Electronic Word of Mouth Supporting Plan

The last and most influential variable on purchase intention is E-WOM. Because there is barely any difference in E-WOM influence between Gen Z and millennials, the suggestions will be common ideas for increasing E-WOM.

1. Invest more in Service Quality and Learning Journey

According to the literature review, E-WOM is the result of a customer's experience with a product. Therefore, Cetta has to guarantee that all students who enroll in Cetta's class can experience what has become Cetta UVP as an online class and are satisfied with the learning quality provided. Ensure that the Cetta vision, learning, and other brand experiences, as well as culture, are well-transmitted to all students, without exception.

- Cetta should conduct a comprehensive customer journey analysis to understand the student's experience from the moment they enroll until they complete their studies at Cetta. The goal is to find ways to maintain student motivation throughout their learning journey at Cetta.
- Cetta should consider increasing the class quality control team to include more members, as the current setup with only one person may not allow for comprehensive monitoring of more than 200 recorded class sessions in Mandarin and Japanese Class. Cetta can ensure an enhanced quality control process and provide a better learning experience for the students through expanding the team.

2. Referral Program

Implement a member get member program that offers discounts and cashback to both people who give and receive referrals. This could lead to satisfied customers recommending the product to their friends and family, generating significant E-WOM.

Since many years, the member get member program has been popular in traditional education businesses. For example, Primagama, one of the oldest offline courses in Indonesia, has a program in which those who bring one friend to join the course will receive 10% off the monthly tuition fee, while the invited person will also receive 10% off the registration fee. Because of this program, Primagama now has hundreds of branches throughout Indonesia. Cetta should also implement a "Member Get Member" program (Figure 15), in which every student can participate and contribute to the organic promotion of Cetta.

Figure 15. Member Get Member Information Card to be Published.

3. Build a Strong Community

In this Web3.0 era, which every business must be customer centric, business who wins the customer, wins the competition. Nowadays many brands build their own brand community that has goals to boost and maintain their brand engagement with customer. Telepresence and social presence in online communities on brand engagement which create a strong sense of community can increase consumer engagement, resulting in positive E-WOM [30].

One of the most successful brand with the community in Indonesia is from the skin care industry, called the "Skingame" (Figure 16). It has a very strong community presence online and E-WOM, from the testimony to their sales, that they went so viral that it has bunch of review videos uploaded in TikTok and Instagram. Customers are even competing to become members of the company's exclusive community, known as the "Skingamewarrior," who additionally have proven that they can convert a normal customer into a loyal customer while maintaining it that way. This led to very successful sales of Skingame products in all Indonesian e-commerce sites.

Figure 16. Skingame Instagram Account and Skingamewarrior Community by Skingame

2) **Continuous Monitoring and Adjustment:** With the constantly evolving algorithms of social media platforms, businesses need to stay vigilant and adapt their strategies accordingly. The algorithms used by social media companies can change frequently, affecting how content is prioritized and displayed to users. Therefore, businesses must stay informed and keep up with these changes to ensure their content reaches the intended audience effectively. All of the above recommendations can be implemented in various ways. It will take some trial and error in various application formats before a suitable strategy that aligns with the business nature of Cetta Online Class can be discovered.

Finally, the marketing strategy's effectiveness can be measured by the return on investment (ROI) generated from the allocated marketing budget and its impact on driving sales growth. To achieve and potentially exceed these goals, a well-defined standard operating procedure.

3) **Implementation Plan & Justification:** Based on all the business solution ideas described above, the recommendation action plan for Cetta Online Class is explained in Figure 17.

Objectives	Action Item	Details	Month 2023											
			4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12			
Maximize Simultaneous Media Communication	New Design	Re-Design social media, make a new face of Cetta's instagram profile.	█											
	Senior Content Writer recruitment	Recruit 1 senior writer, for all 4 language department.		█	█									
	Specified Social Media Specialist recruitment	Recruit 1 social media specialist for each language department.		█	█									
	External content creators Recruitment	Recruit 3 Content Creators for each language department.		█	█									
	Training	Training new talents for their new positions and responsibilities.				█								
User-Generated Social Media Communication Supporting Plan	Content Contests and Challenges	Make a Montly Contest of best class, open for all students. pick 10 best picture for the voting from Instagram story vote.		█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
	Student Stories and Testimonials	Choose 3-5 best student who has minimum 1000 followers in instagram, ask them to create a reels video. Cetta's Intagram upload and ask them for collaboration post.		█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
	Student Ambassador Program	Build a concept of Student Ambassador Program. Start the Student ambassador Program			█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
Electronic Word of Mouth Supporting Plan	Invest more in Service Quality and Learning Journey	conduct a comprehensive customer journey analysis, figure out additional facility to enhance learning experience quality			█	█	█							
		discuss with Operation team and plan with HR about recruit more people to the quality control team.					█							
	Referral Program	make a finance scheme for a Member get Member program.			█									
		Start the Member get member Program				█	█	█	█	█	█	█	█	
Build a Strong Community	Build a concept of a Community, which focus in maintaining students retention and CLV. Generate loyal students.					█								

Figure 17. Applicable Action Plan for Cetta Online Class

V. CONCLUSIONS

From the quantitative calculation results it can be concluded that simultaneous method has the highest influence level (32%). Simultaneous media communication means Cetta should strive for a balanced and integrated communication strategy that incorporates all three elements which includes Firm-Created social media communication, User Generated social media communication, and E-WOM. Additionally, the partial analysis results for each variable indicate that E-WOM has the highest influence (25.7%), followed by User Generated (19.7%) and Firm-Created (17.6%).

Furthermore, the comparative test between GenZ and Millennials reveals that GenZ has an overall higher influence, which aligns with the findings in the literature review that GenZ is even more tech-savvy than Millennials. So, based on the question research the answers are:

1. E-WOM is the most influential factor, but it is surpassed by simultaneous social media communication, which is an integrated communication strategy that incorporates all three elements, including firm-created social media, user-generated social media, and E-WOM.
2. GenZ respondents have more influence than millennials, which includes both firm-created and user-generated influence. Millennials exceeded Gen Z in E-WOM by 0.02%.
3. As explained above, the recommended strategies are provided for each variable, which has the main point to maximize simultaneous communication.
 - a. Firm-Created Social Media Communication Plan
 - New Design
 - Social media creative team recruitment.
 - b. User-Generated Social Media Communication Supporting Plan
 - Content Contests and Challenges
 - Student Stories and Testimonials
 - Student Ambassador Program
 - c. Electronic Word of Mouth Supporting Plan
 - Invest more in Service Quality and Learning Journey
 - Referral Program
 - Build a Strong Community

Implementing simultaneous media communication could require some resource adjustments and investments in terms of content creation, community management, and online conversation monitoring. However, the long-term benefits in terms of brand visibility, customer engagement, and increased purchase intent make it a strategy worth considering for Cetta. Overall, maximizing simultaneous media communication enables Cetta to develop a comprehensive and integrated marketing strategy that leverages the strengths of firm-created social media, user-generated social media, and e-WOM, resulting in increased brand presence and student enrollment.

A. Recommendations

Future research should continue to test the effectiveness of implementation plans within the company, or research it in different businesses/multi-brands, particularly businesses outside the education or service industries. It is because the way a product is delivered in social media differs from the way a physically available product and a service product are delivered.

Future researchers can also use other methods to research purchase intention, such as in-depth interviews with respondents, to obtain more varied information than a questionnaire with already available answers.

REFERENCES

1. Murad, D. F., Hassan, R., Heryadi, Y., Wijanarko, B. D., and Titan 2020. The Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia (Face to face versus online learning). In 2020 Third International Conference on Vocational Education and Electrical Engineering (ICVEE) (Surabaya, Indonesia, Oct. 2020), 1-4.
2. Innovation Factory. 2019. i360 report Edutech industry in Indonesia. www.theravenry.com. Accessed: 2023-01-02
3. Munadzdofah, O. 2018. Pentingnya Bahasa Inggris, China, dan Jepang sebagai bahasa komunikasi bisnis di era globalisasi. *Vocatio J. Ilm. Ilmu Adm, Sekr.* 1, 2 (Mar. 2018), 58-73.
4. Chauhan, K. and Pillai, A. 2013. Role of content strategy in social media brand communities: a case of higher education institutes in India. *J. Prod. Brand Manag.* 22, 1 (Feb. 2013), 40-51.
5. Kotler, P., Kartajaya, H. and Setiawan, I. 2019. *Marketing 3.0: from products to customers to the human spirit*. Marketing Wisdom. K. Kompella, ed. Springer. 139-156.
6. Ahmed, M. A. and Zahid, Z. 2014. Role of social media marketing to enhance CRM and brand equity in terms of purchase intention. *Asian J. Manag. Res.* 4, 3 (2014), 533-549.
7. Brodie, R. J., Ilic, A., Juric, B. and Hollebeek, L. 2013. Consumer engagement in a virtual brand community: an exploratory analysis. *J. Bus. Res.* 66, 1 (Jan. 2013), 105-114.

8. Kaplan, A. M. and Haenlein, M. 2010. Users of the world, unite! The challenges and opportunities of Social Media. *Bus. Horiz.* 53, 1 (Jan. 2010), 59-68.
9. Labrecque, L. I., Vor Dem Esche, J., Mathwick, C., Novak, T. P. and Hofacker, C. F. 2013. Consumer power: evolution in the digital age. *J. Interact. Mark.* 27, 4 (Nov. 2013), 257-269.
10. Munandar, D., Ananda, F. R., Syaifuddin, S., Lubis, Y. and Nasib, N. 2022. The role of student trust in mediating service quality and student reputation against E-WOM. *J. Educ. Sci. Technol.* 8, 2 (2022).
11. Kudeshia, C. and Kumar, A. 2017. Social eWOM: does it affect the brand attitude and purchase intention of brands? *Manag. Res. Rev.* 40, 3 (Mar. 2017), 310-330.
12. Kotler, P. and Keller, K. L. 2012. *Marketing management*. Pearson Education Limited.
13. Abubakar, A. M., Ilkan, M. and Sahin, P. 2016. eWOM, eReferral and gender in the virtual community. *Mark. Intell. Plan.* 34, 5 (Aug. 2016), 692-710.
14. Gruen, T. W., Osmonbekov, T. and Czaplewski, A. J. 2006. eWOM: the impact of customer-to-customer online know-how exchange on customer value and loyalty. *J. Bus. Res.* 59, 4 (Apr. 2006), 449-456.
15. Azhar, M., Sutiono, H. T. and Wisnalmawati, W. 2021. The effect of digital marketing and electronic word of mouth on purchase decisions and customer satisfaction. *Semin. Nas. Inform. Semnasif.* 1, 1 (Nov. 2021), 289-305.
16. Hennig-Thurau, T., Gwinner, K. P., Walsh, G. and Gremler, D. D. 2004. Electronic word-of-mouth via consumer-opinion platforms: what motivates consumers to articulate themselves on the Internet? *J. Interact. Mark.* 18, 1 (Feb. 2004), 38-52.
17. Jalilvand, M. R. and Samiei, N. 2012. The effect of electronic word of mouth on brand image and purchase intention: an empirical study in the automobile industry in Iran. *Mark. Intell. Plan.* 30, 4 (Jun. 2012), 460-476.
18. Fotis, J., Buhalis, D. and Rossides, N. 2012. Social media use and impact during the holiday travel planning process. In *Information and communication technologies in tourism 2012* (Vienna, 2012), 13-24.
19. Zhang, K. and Sarvary, M. 2015. Differentiation with user-generated content. *Manag. Sci.* 61, 4 (Apr. 2015), 898-914.
20. Wu, P. C. S., Yeh, G. Y. -Y. and Hsiao, C. -R. 2011. The effect of store image and service quality on brand image and purchase intention for private label brands. *Australas. Mark. J.* 19, 1 (Feb. 2011), 30-39.
21. Zeng, D., Chen, H., Lusch, R. and Li, S. -H. 2010. Social media analytics and intelligence. *IEEE Intell. Syst.* 25, 6 (Nov. 2010), 13-16.
22. Kim, J. and Lee, J. -E. R. 2011. The Facebook paths to happiness: effects of the number of Facebook friends and self-presentation on subjective well-being. *Cyberpsychology Behav. Soc. Netw.* 14, 6 (Jun. 2011), 359-364.
23. Chu, S. -C. and Kim, Y. 2011. Determinants of consumer engagement in electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) in social networking sites. *Int. J. Advert.* 30, 1 (Jan. 2011), 47-75.
24. Dimock, M. 2019. Defining generations: where millennials end and generation Z begins. *Pew Res. Cent.* 17, 1 (2019), 1-7.
25. Thomas, M. R., Kavya, V. and Monica, M. 2018. Online website cues influencing the purchase intention of generation Z mediated by trust. *Indian J. Commer. Manag. Stud.* IX, 1 (Jan. 2018), 13.
26. McCormick, K. 2016. Celebrity endorsements: influence of a product-endorser match on Millennials attitudes and purchase intentions. *J. Retail. Consum. Serv.* 32, (Sep. 2016), 39-45.
27. Belk, R. W. 1985. Materialism: trait aspects of living in the material world. *J. Consum. Res.* 12, 3 (Dec. 1985), 265-280.
28. Alrwashdeh, M., Emeagwali, O. L. and Aljuhmani, H. Y. 2019. The effect of electronic word of mouth communication on purchase intention and brand image: an applicant smartphone brands in North Cyprus. *Manag. Sci. Lett.* 9, 4 (2019), 505-518.
29. Schivinski, B. and Dabrowski, D. 2013. The effect of social media communication on consumer perceptions of brands. *J. Mark. Commun.* 22, 2 (2013), 189-214.
30. Algharabat, R., Rana, N. P., Dwivedi, Y. K., Alalwan, A. A. and Qasem, Z. 2018. The effect of telepresence, social presence and involvement on consumer brand engagement: An empirical study of non-profit organizations. *J. Retail. Consum. Serv.* 40, (Jan. 2018), 139-149.

Cite this Article: Ali Akbar, Dina Dellyana (2023). Maximizing Simultaneous Social Media Communication: A Study on Purchase Intention among Millennials and Generation Z in the Online Language Learning Industry. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 6(6), 3635-3656